

Evaluate the Effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme on Knowledge of Infection Control Measures among Nursing Students

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ABSTRACT

Infectious diseases are continuing threat to all patients, regardless of the age, gender, lifestyle, ethnic background and socioeconomic status. Health care is always facing new danger from incurable infections. Nurses play an important role in the health care team, they need to have current knowledge related to emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases. Student nurses are often exposed to various infections during their clinical experience as a part of curriculum. As a member of health care team, nursing students have huge responsibility to protect themselves, patients and other members of health team.

The aim of the study was to impart the knowledge on infection control measures through video assisted programme among nursing students in order to protect themselves and patients in the clinical field. A quasi-experimental study, one group pre- and posttest design, 150 nursing students was conducted in selected nursing college. Pretest was assessed with demographic profile of nursing students and knowledge questionnaire followed by videos was displayed to the participants regarding specific infection control measures of Hand hygiene and personal protective equipment's (PPE). The post test was conducted after 7 days with same tools used in pretest assessment. The level of knowledge on hand washing technique after video assisted teaching programme on infection control measures increased significantly by 50% in the posttest with mean difference of 2.18, $t=14.76$; the level of knowledge on PPE after video assisted teaching programme on infection control measures increased significantly by 57.4% in the posttest with mean difference of 1.02, $t=14.42$ at 0.05 level of significant. Statistically significant association between the pretest level of knowledge on hand washing with scores of nursing programme ($\chi^2 = 39.76$, $p < 0.001$), year of experience ($\chi^2 = 33.19$, $p < 0.001$), year of study ($\chi^2 = 41.35$, $p < 0.001$); association between the pretest level of knowledge on PPE with scores of gender ($\chi^2 = 15.50$, $p < 0.001$) nursing programme ($\chi^2 = 54.07$, $p < 0.001$), year of experience ($\chi^2 = 41.65$, $p < 0.001$), year of study ($\chi^2 = 70.46$, $p < 0.001$) was found. Video-assisted teaching programme was effective to enhance the knowledge of hand washing and use of PPE as infection prevention control measures among nursing students in order to protect themselves and patients their practice field and community.

KEY WORDS: hand washing, infection control, knowledge, video assisted teaching programme, personal protective equipment

INTRODUCTION:

Infectious diseases are great threat to all members of health care team and patients regardless of the age, gender, lifestyle, ethnic background and socioeconomic status. They cause suffering, death and impose a financial burden

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on the society. The history of infection control practices commence to take place in hospitals in 1840 when the importance and influence of hand washing was brought to keen attention in the medical area. Then in 1854, Florence Nightingale was pioneer to document the importance of hygienic environment for good health. Her work is the first ever evidence highlighting the relation of good health to hygienic environmental factors (air, water, light, efficient drainage and cleanliness). Infection control is one of the most important aspects of contemporary hospital management^[1].

The World Health Organization (WHO) defined standard precautions as meant to reduce the

risk of transmission of blood borne and other pathogens from both recognized and unrecognized sources, they are the basic level of infection precautions which are essential in the care of all patients. Nursing has important role in the prevention of infectious diseases in the care of persons and families having infectious diseases^[2].

As per the health and safety executive guidelines (1992) on personal protective equipments (PPE), "It is defined as 'all equipment which is intended to be worn or held by a person at work and which protects him against one or more risks to his health or safety'". PPE are safety helmets, masks, gloves, eye protection, gown, and safety footwear. It is to paid attention towards the proper fitting PPE, wearing poorly fitting PPE can lead to a number of problems such as excessive sweating, friction, discomfort, also finger and hand muscle fatigue^[3].

As per Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) guidelines (1996) the following standard precautions measures replace the old universal precautions system such as (a) Hand washing: wash hands before and after touching the patients, equipments, patient surfaces, before and after any procedure and immediately whenever required to avoid the transfer of microorganisms. (b) Gloves: Clean and sterile gloves are necessary to wear when touching body fluids, blood, secretions, excretions, and contaminated items. (c) Masks, eye protection, face shields: Masks, eye protection and a face shield to protect mucous membranes of the eyes, nose, and mouth during procedures. (d) Gowns: Clean and sterile gown to protect skin and to prevent soiling of clothing of Health care workers during procedures, exposure to splashes or sprays of blood, body fluids, secretions, or excretions. (e) Patient care equipments: the equipment gets soiled when exposed to blood, body fluids, secretions, and excretions. The equipments used to infected patients, there may be a chance of transfer of microorganisms from one patient to others or to environments. Hence, taking care of patient care equipments, process of cleaning, sterilizing and discarding procedure adopted appropriately. (f) Environmental control: The policies and guidelines of the hospital must ensure the adequate infection prevention and control procedures for the routine care, cleaning of environmental surfaces, taking care of bedside equipment, beds, bed rails, and other frequently touched surfaces, and ensure that these procedures are being followed as per the guidelines/ standard operating procedure or institutional policy^[4].

Health care is always facing new danger from

incurable infections. Nurses being important role in the health care team, they need to have adequate knowledge and skills regarding emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases. Nurses have to play multidimensional role and their skills have to be combined with a specialized knowledge and practice base to ensure improved health status of the family. Student nurses are often exposed to various infections during their clinical education, and as health care workers, nursing students have huge responsibility to protect themselves, patients and their families from challenging work environment. It is very important for the nurse educators to involve the student nurses in understanding the transmission, risk factors, causes, control and preventive aspects of infectious diseases. The aim of the study to impart the knowledge on infection control measures through video assisted programme among nurses in order to protect themselves and patients their practice field and community.

Statement of the Problem: A study to evaluate the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme on knowledge of Infection Control Measures among nursing students. The objectives of the study were to: 1) assess the demographic profile of the nursing students; 2) assess the level of knowledge on hand washing technique before and after video assisted teaching programme on knowledge of infection control measures among nursing students; 3) assess the level of knowledge on use of personal protective measures before and after video assisted teaching programme on knowledge of infection control measures among nursing students; 4) evaluate the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge of infection control measures among nursing students; 5) Associate the demographic profile of the nursing students with pretest level of knowledge on hand washing among nursing students and 6) Associate the background profile of the nursing students with pretest level of knowledge on use of personal protective measures among nursing students.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

The study was aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge of infection control measures among nursing students in Bhopal Nursing College, BMHRC, Bhopal. A quantitative research approach and pre-experimental one group pretest and post test research design was used. The sample of 150 nursing students of GNM and Post Basic BSc nursing were the samples of this study. They were recruited through probability

random sampling techniques used in this study. Each group consists of 25 participants. The tools used for data collection were background profile questionnaire, structured questionnaire on hand washing techniques with 10 items and use of personal protective equipments (PPE) with 15 items.

The tools used in this study were validated by nursing and medical experts. Video program on infection control was developed which includes source of infection, routes of transmission, chain of infection, barriers of infection, hand washing technique and wearing - removal (donning and doffing) of PPE. It was edited and structured by members of research team and it was validated by experts. The conceptual framework used in this study was general system theory with input, process and output. The data collection was done from September 2015 to October 2015. The purpose of the study was explained to each candidate. Ethical and administrative permissions obtained from the institution. First day, the pretest data collected with demographic profile questionnaire, structured questionnaire on hand washing techniques with 10 items and use of personal protective equipments (PPE) with 15 items and the same day video assisted teaching programme implemented and after 7th day the post test was conducted with

same group by using same questionnaire. The data were analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics (Figure 1).

RESULTS:

Among 150 nursing students, 24(16%) students were in the age group of 19 years and majority 112(74.6%) were in the age group of 20 years and above. Majority of the participants 114(74%) were female. 130 (86%) undergone GNM course. 20 (14%) belongs to Post Basic Bsc Nursing students (First year). In regards to previous clinical experiences of nursing students, majority, 130(86%) nursing students had no clinical experience, 10(6.6%) had 1-2 years of clinical experience and 10(6.6% had 3-5 years of clinical experience.

The above (Table 1) shows that, before video teaching program the level of knowledge on hand washing was 7.3% (11) and it was increased after the intervention 57.3%(86) ie., the level of knowledge on hand washing technique after video assisted teaching programme on infection control measures increased significantly by 50% in the posttest.

The above (Table 2) shows that before and after video assisted teaching programme on knowledge of hand washing technique, the mean score was

Table 1: Assess the knowledge on hand washing technique before and after video assisted teaching programme on infection control measures (n=150).

Hand washing technique	Inadequate knowledge		Moderate knowledge		Adequate knowledge	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Before video assisted teaching programme	78	52	61	40.7	11	7.3
After video assisted teaching programme	07	4.66	57	38	86	57.33

Figure 1: Assess the knowledge on use of PPE before and after video assisted teaching programme on infection control measures.

Table 2: Evaluate the effectiveness of video assisted programme on knowledge of hand washing technique (n=150).

Knowledge on Hand washing technique	Mean score	SD	Difference in mean	t-value
Before video assisted teaching programme	5.44	1.38	2.18	14.76
After video assisted teaching programme	7.62	1.158		df=149, p<0.05 level of significance *

Table 3: Evaluate the effectiveness of video assisted programme on knowledge of use of PPE (n=150).

Knowledge on Use of PPE	Mean score	SD	Difference in mean	t-value
Before video assisted teaching programme	8.86	2.48	1.02	14.42
After video assisted teaching programme	12.32	1.50		df=149, p<0.05 level of significance *

5.44, with SD 1.38; mean score was 7.62 and SD 1.158 respectively. Hence the effect of video assisted programme on knowledge of hand washing was found significant at 0.05 level with t value of 14.76. The above (Table 3) shows that, before and after video assisted teaching programme on knowledge of use of PPE, the mean score was 8.86, with SD 2.48; mean score was 12.32 and SD 1.50 respectively. Hence the effect of video assisted programme on knowledge of PPE was found significant at 0.05 level with t value of 14.42.

DISCUSSION:

Associate the background profile of the nursing students with knowledge on hand washing among nursing students. Statistically the significant association between the pretest level of knowledge on hand washing with scores of the type of nursing programme ($\chi^2=39.76$, $df=1$), year of experience ($\chi^2=33.19$, $df=4$), year of study ($\chi^2=41.35$, $df=6$) were significant at 0.05 level of significance and age and gender were not significant.

Associate the background profile of the nursing students with knowledge on use of personal protective measures among nursing students. Statistically the significant association between the pretest level of knowledge on PPE with scores of the Gender ($\chi^2=15.51$, $df=1$), the type of nursing programme ($\chi^2=54.07$, $df=1$), year of experience ($\chi^2=41.65$, $df=4$), year of study ($\chi^2=70.47$, $df=6$) were significant at 0.05 level.

Implications:

The findings of the study have implications in nursing education, nursing administration and nursing research. Video assisted teaching programme can be

incorporated as blended teaching methods to impart the knowledge on infection control. Emphasis on hand washing technique of nurses will reflect on the quality of care. Conduction of inservice education among nurses through video assisted demonstration of hand washing and use of PPE to prevent the infection control measures. It provides the model for teaching to impart the knowledge and can be utilized for the other procedure in the clinical areas.

Recommendations:

Demonstration vs video assisted teaching on knowledge of hand washing can be conducted. Similar studies with large sample size can be conducted to generalize the study findings. Practice of infection control measures can be measured with structured check list or standardized tool. A comparative study can be done on nurses, nursing students, paramedical staffs and students or with different health care personnel.

CONCLUSION:

A video assisted teaching programme is the effective strategy to improve the knowledge of nursing students on hand washing techniques and use of PPE to prevent the infection and control measures. It ensures the safety of the patients as well as health care personnel. As nurses are the important members of the health care team they must acquaint themselves with adequate knowledge with proper updating to protect themselves and community against infectious diseases.

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